

RESOLUTION OF *tris*-PHENYLBIGUANIDE COBALTIC CHLORIDE AND A STUDY OF THE KINETICS OF RACEMISATION OF THE LAEVO-GYRATE

BY SONIL KUMAR SIDDHANTA, NIHAR KUMAR DUTT AND PRIYADARANJAN RÂY

Cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanide chloride was resolved through the fractionation of its chloro-*d*-tartrate, the less soluble *l*-chloro-*d*-tartrate separating out first with $[M]_D^{25} = -285^\circ$. From the mother-liquor *d*-chloro-*d*-tartrate was obtained with $[M]_D^{25} = +290^\circ$.

From the two diastereoisomerides the pure optically active components of the chloride, sulphate and nitrate of the complex base were obtained with $[M]_D^{25} = \pm 250^\circ, \pm 2469^\circ, \pm 2437^\circ$ respectively.

The velocity of inversion of the *l*-cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanide chloride and its temperature coefficient were measured, and the activation energy of its transformation was calculated from Arrhenius's equation. The value of its activation energy was found to be equal to 9700 calories approx. This is considerably lower than that of cobaltic *tris*-biguanide chloride (13,930 cal.), previously reported (Rây and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 81).

Rây and Dutt (*this Journal*, 1941, 18, 289) resolved the cobaltic *tris*-biguanide chloride into its optically active enantiomerides. They also showed that a solution of the chloro-*d*-tartrate of the racemoid complex base exhibited the phenomenon of asymmetric transformation of the second order as described by Kuhn (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 49). In order to study the effect of substitution in the ligand on the stability and the properties of the active forms of the complex, as also on the character of the diastereomerides through which the resolution is effected, the present work on the resolution of cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanide complex and the study of the kinetics of its racemisation was undertaken.

An account of the preparation and properties of cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanidine and its various salts has been given by Rây and Bhattacharya (*this Journal*, 1939, 16, 629). The resolution of this complex was effected, as in the case of *tris*-biguanide cobaltic complex, through the fractionation of its chloro-*d*-tartrate. The phenomenon of asymmetric transformation of the second order, which was observed during the progress of fractional crystallisation of the chloro-*d*-tartrate of the *tris*-biguanide complex, was not, however, found to occur in the present case. The two diastereomerides separated here normally from the solution on fractional crystallisation. As in the previous case, the laevo-gyrate, being less soluble, separated out first. This affords another evidence against Werner's generalisation regarding the comparative solubility of the chloro-*d*-tartrates of the optically active antipodes of cobaltic complexes (Werner, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 865), which assumed that the *d*-chloro-*d*-tartrate of the cobaltic complexes should always form the less soluble variety (cf. also Jaeger, "Spatial Arrangement of Atomic Systems and Optical Activity", McGraw-Hill Book Co. Inc., 1930, p. 92). There is therefore no direct relationship between the space configuration of the molecules and their relative or absolute solubility.

From the two diastereoisomerides the pure optically active enantiomers of the chloride, sulphate and nitrate of the complex base were obtained with specific and molecular rotations of $[\alpha]_D^{25} = \pm 337^\circ, \pm 300^\circ, \pm 315^\circ$, and $[M]_D^{25} = \pm 2500^\circ, \pm 2469^\circ$ and $\pm 2437^\circ$ respectively. The corresponding molecular rotation values for chloride and nitrate of the complex cobaltic *tris*-ethylenediamine are: $[M]_D = \pm 608^\circ$ and $\pm 562^\circ$ respectively. A higher rotation value for the phenylbiguanide cobaltic complex, like that of the corresponding *tris*-biguanide complex, is indicative of a lower degree of symmetry of these complexes.

The active isomerides are quite stable in the solid state. In aqueous solutions they are fairly stable at lower temperatures, but begin, however, to racemise as the temperature rises. The velocity of racemisation of the pure active *l*-chloride has been measured and studied at different temperatures. From the temperature coefficient of the specific reaction rate, the activation energy for racemisation has been calculated. The results seem to support the mechanism of transformation suggested by Rây and Dutt (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

The orange coloured crystals of *tris*-phenylbiguanide chloride were prepared and purified following the method described by Rây and Bhattacharya (*loc. cit.*). {Found: N, 28.01; Co, 8.04. $[\text{Co}(\text{PhBigH})_3] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 28.32; Co, 7.96 per cent}, where PhBigH = one molecule of phenylbiguanide = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_5$.

r-Cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanide chloro-*d*-tartrate was prepared by double decomposition from the cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanide chloride and one molecule of silver *d*-tartrate. The solution filtered from the silver chloride was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The crystals were left in air till their weight became constant. The substance forms reddish yellow microcrystalline solid, moderately soluble in water.

{Found: Cl, 4.01; Co, 6.57; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$, 16.18. $\left[\text{Co}(\text{PhBigH})_3 \right] \begin{matrix} \text{Cl} \\ \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6(d) \end{matrix}$, $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 3.95; Co, 6.56; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$, 16.45 per cent}.

It loses all its water when kept in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 (conc.).

l-Cobaltic *tris*-Phenylbiguanide chloro-*d*-tartrate.—The laevo component was obtained from the above described partial racemate in the form of bright yellow microcrystals by fractional crystallisation of the latter in aqueous solution. The rotation of the crystals was found to increase on repeated recrystallisation to a maximum value, when the crystals were finally washed first with cold water, then with alcohol, and afterwards dried in air. It is somewhat less soluble than the partial racemate. {Found:

Cl, 3.85; Co, 6.61; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$, 16.22. $l\text{-} \left[\text{Co}(\text{PhBigH})_3 \right] \begin{matrix} \text{Cl} \\ \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6(d) \end{matrix}$, $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 3.95; Co, 6.56; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$, 16.45 per cent}. $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -285^\circ$; $[M]_D^{25} = -2564^\circ$.

d-Cobaltic *tris*-Phenylbiguanide chloro-*d*-tartrate.—The mother-liquor from the laevo salt, described above, was treated with an excess of alcohol for complete pre-

precipitation. The crystals separated were dissolved in the least quantity of water and kept in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 (conc.). A crop of impure laevo salt first separated out. This was removed and the filtrate in turn was subjected to the same treatment as before. The process was repeated with the more soluble fraction in each successive case until the rotation of the finally separated product became maximum and constant. This was washed and dried as usual. {Found: Cl, 3.81; Co, 6.48; $C_6H_4O_6$, 16.28.

d - $\left[Co(PhBigH)_3\right]Cl$, $7H_2O$ requires Cl, 3.95; Co, 6.56; $C_6H_4O_6$, 16.45 per cent).

$[\alpha]_D^{25} = +290^\circ$; $[M]_D^{25} = +2609^\circ$.

l-Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide sulphate was obtained as an orange-red micro-crystalline solid from a solution of the laevo component of the complex chloro-*d*-tartrate by precipitation with a cold saturated solution of ammonium sulphate. The crystals were washed and dried as usual. {Found: Co, 7.14. *l*- $[Co(PhBigH)_3]_2(SO_4)_3, 10H_2O$ requires Co, 7.16 per cent}. $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -300^\circ$; $[M]_D^{25} = -4938^\circ$.

d-Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide sulphate was obtained in the same manner as its laevo isomer from the corresponding *d*-chloro *d*-tartrate and ammonium sulphate. It is more soluble than its *l*-isomer. {Found: Co, 7.12. *d*- $[Co(PhBigH)_3]_2(SO_4)_3, 10H_2O$ requires Co, 7.16 per cent}. $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +300^\circ$; $[M]_D^{25} = +4938^\circ$.

l-Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide chloride was obtained by double decomposition from the complex *l*-sulphate and barium chloride. The solution was then filtered from the precipitated barium sulphate and evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 (conc.). The product was dried in air. {Found: Co, 8.08. *l*- $[Co(PhBigH)_3]Cl_3, 2.5H_2O$ requires Co, 7.97 per cent}. $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -337^\circ$; $[M]_D^{25} = -2500^\circ$.

d-Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide chloride was prepared like its *l*-isomer from the corresponding *d*-sulphate and barium chloride. It has the same composition as the *l*-chloride. (Found: Co, 8.05. Calc. Co, 7.97 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +335^\circ$; $[M]_D^{25} = +2485^\circ$.

l-Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide nitrate was also obtained by double decomposition between the *l*-sulphate and barium nitrate. It is less soluble than the chloride. {Found: Co, 7.51. *l*- $[Co(PhBigH)_3](NO_3)_3$ requires Co, 7.60 per cent}. $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -315^\circ$; $[M]_D^{25} = -2437^\circ$.

d-Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide nitrate was prepared like its *l*-isomer from the *d*-sulphate and barium nitrate. (Found: Co, 7.46. Calc. Co, 7.60 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +320^\circ$; $[M]_D^{25} = +2483^\circ$.

All measurements were made in a Franz Schmidt and Haensch polarimeter with a trisected field of vision and provided with an electrical heating arrangement by which the temperature could be maintained constant to $\pm 0.1^\circ$. A sodium vapour lamp was used as the source of illumination.

Cobalt was estimated as $CoSO_4$ after decomposition of the substance with conc. H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 . Tartaric acid was estimated by the iodate method (Goldenberg, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1908, 57, 47; Unger and Haynes, *Analyst*, 1946, 71, 141).

Kinetics of Racemisation

The velocity constant of inversion, $l\text{-salt} \rightleftharpoons d\text{-salt}$ for the active complex ion was deduced from the equation,

$$dx/dt = k(a-x) - kx = k(a-2x)$$

where a = initial conc. of the active salt; x = conc. of its optical antipode formed by inversion after a time t , and k = the velocity constant of inversion of the active forms.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Integrating, } k &= \frac{1}{2t} \ln \frac{a}{(a-2x)} = \frac{2.303}{2t} \log \frac{a}{(a-2x)} \\ &= \frac{2.303}{2t} \log_{10} \frac{R_0}{R_t} \end{aligned}$$

where R_0 = initial rotation, R_t = rotation after a time t in minutes.

$$\text{Hence, } T \text{ (half-life)} = \frac{2.303}{2k} \log_{10} 2.$$

The velocity constant was measured at 46.2° with solutions of different concentrations of the laevo-rotate with the following results.

TABLE I

I. Conc. (mol./litre) $\times 10^3 = 6.74$.						
Time (min.)	...	0	180	360	540	
α_D	...	1.68	1.56	1.45	1.35	
$k \times 10^4$	...	—	2.06	2.04	2.03	Mean = 2.05
II. Conc. $\times 10^3 = 13.52$.						
Time (min.)	...	0	180	360	540	
α_D	...	3.37	3.13	2.90	2.70	
$k \times 10^4$	...	—	2.05	2.08	2.05	Mean = 2.06
III. Conc. $\times 10^3 = 17.05$.						
Time (min.)	...	0	180	360	540	
α_D	...	4.20	3.90	3.63	3.37	
$k \times 10^4$	...	—	2.05	2.04	2.04	Mean = 2.04

Therefore, k at $46.2^\circ = 2.05$ (mean).

The results show that within the limits of the concentration employed the transformation is strictly of the monomolecular type. This is illustrated by plotting the logarithm of the rotation values against time in minutes, which gives straight lines as required by the equation. The velocity constant k can therefore be evaluated by multiplying the slope of the line by $2.303/2$ (cf. Fig. 1).

For the measurement of temperature coefficient of the specific inversion rate an 1% solution of the *l*-gyrate in one dm. tube was used. The results are tabulated below

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

and the Fig. 2 shows that a straight line is obtained by plotting the logarithm of the specific inversion rate against the reciprocal of the absolute temperature.

TABLE II

t°	$1/T$	$k \times 10^4$	$\log k$	Half-life.
40.2°	0.003193	1.53	-3.815	37.75 hours
43.5°	0.003160	1.81	-3.742	31.92
46.2°	0.003133	2.05	-3.688	28.05
50.2°	0.003094	2.46	-3.609	23.50
54.6°	0.003053	3.05	-3.516	18.94

The activation energy for racemisation was then obtained from the slope of the line on the basis of Arrhenius's equation :

$$\frac{d \ln k}{dt} = \frac{E}{RT^2}, \text{ where } E = \text{the activation energy.}$$

$$\text{Integrating, } \log k = \frac{-E}{2.303 RT} + C (\text{constant})$$

$$\text{Or, } \log k_2/k_1 = \frac{E}{2.303 R} \times \frac{(T_2 - T_1)}{T_2 T_1} \text{ (between the limits } T_2 \text{ and } T_1)$$

Expressed in the exponential form, $k = s e^{-E/RT}$, where s is the Arrhenius's constant.

The value of E is equal to 9640 calories as obtained from the slope of the curve, and 9720 calories from the integrated equation between the limits T_2 and T_1 .

When $\log_{10} s$ is calculated from the value of E , it becomes equal to 1.13 only with k expressed in sec^{-1} . This is rather exceptionally low for a unimolecular reaction, which usually lies between 13 and 14. In the case of cobaltic *tris*-biguanide complex also a similar low value of 4.16 for $\log_{10} s$ was observed for the inversion of its laevo enantiomorph (Rây and Dutt, *loc. cit.*). This indicates that the specific rate of inversion, or rather the probability factor P of Arrhenius's constant ($s = PZ$), is unusually low in these cobaltic biguanide complexes; and much more so in the case of the phenylbiguanide complex. As already suggested in the earlier paper, the phenomenon may be attributed to an unusual delay in the specific energy transfer, which means an increase in the time lag between pre-activation and critical activation, or, as now expressed, between the formation of activated complex and its transformation, with the result that most of the activated molecules suffer deactivation before the change occurs. This time lag, and hence the chances of deactivation are likely to be greater in the case of the comparatively complicated and heavy molecules of the phenylbiguanide complex.

A comparative idea of the stability and optical properties of *l*-cobaltic *tris*-biguanide and *l*-cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanide chlorides can be obtained from the following values in Table III.

TABLE III

	$[M]_{500}^{25}$	$k \times 10^4$ (46.2°)	T (half-life).	E (calc.)	$\log_{10} s$
<i>l</i> -[Co(BigH) ₃]Cl ₃ ...	-2103°	2.46	23.5 hrs.	13930	4.16
<i>l</i> -[Co(PhBiH) ₃]Cl ₃ ...	-2500°	2.05	28.05	9700	1.13

Thus the substitution of a phenyl group in biguanide considerably increases its molecular rotation, but reduces its specific inversion rate and its activation energy. The value of Arrhenius's constant is also reduced to an exceedingly low value, nearly 27% of that for the *l*-cobaltic *tris*-biguanide complex, the latter itself being unusually low for a monomolecular reaction.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received June 17, 1950.